

IMPLEMENTATION OF DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT (DRRM) PROGRAM AND ACTIVITIES AMONG SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF SULTAN KUDARAT

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the Implementation of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Program and Activities among schools in the Division of Sultan Kudarat along with Good governance, Risk assessment, Early warning, Knowledge building, and Awareness raising for the school year 2019-2020 among 70 teachers in Central Isulan District. The researcher used the descriptive survey method of research and use a survey questioner to gather the necessary data among respondents of the study. The result of the study on the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management along with Good Governance, Risk Assessment, Early Warning, Knowledge Building, and Awareness Raising was found to be Highly Evident among schools in the Division Sultan Kudarat.

Keywords: *Disaster Risk Reduction Management, Program, Activities, Central Isulan District, Sultan Kudarat, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Republic Act 10121, also known as "Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010", acknowledges the need to "adopt a disaster risk reduction and management approach that is holistic, comprehensive, integrated, and proactive in lessening the socio-economic and environmental impacts of disaster including climate change, and promote the involvement and participation of all sectors and all stakeholders

concerned at all levels, especially in the local community.” This gives a boost to the development of policies and plans, implementation of actions and measures about all aspects of disaster risk reduction management, including good governance, risk assessment and early warning, knowledge building, and awareness raising, reducing underlying risk factors, and preparedness for effective response and early recovery.

The National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Plan serves as the national guide on how sustainable development can be achieved through inclusive growth while building the adaptive capacities of communities; increasing the resilience of vulnerable sectors; and optimizing disaster mitigation opportunities with the end given promoting people’s welfare and security towards gender-responsive and rights-based sustainable development.

Adhering to this, the Department of Education-Sultan Kudarat Division works hard to prevent disasters from happening in the schools to make students free from any disasters. DRRM is now a part of the curriculum and is one of the major concerns of the Department to make children safe in schools from any harm that they may suffer. Now that it is a part of the curriculum, it is being taught in schools and activities accompany the said curriculum. Looking into this, the researcher will try to assess the level of awareness of the teachers and the learners in the implementation of the programs and activities on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM).

Thus, this study draws on the implementation of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) program and activities in Central Isulan District, Division of Sultan Kudarat.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the Implementation of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Program and Activities in the Division of Sultan Kudarat.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) in terms of a. Good governance, b. Risk assessment, c. Early warning, d. Knowledge building, and e. Awareness raising?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used the descriptive survey method of research to the Implementation of the Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program and Activities for the School Year 2019-2020. To (Calderon and Gonzales, 2019) Descriptive survey method of research is also known as a normative survey and it is a fact-finding study with adequate and accurate interpretation.

The data being gathered extensively all about disaster risk reduction management programs and activities. These data were taken from survey questionnaires which were made for further analysis.

The respondents of the study are the 70 teachers in Central Isulan District. The Total Complete Enumeration was used to determine the total number of respondents. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data gathered.

RESULTS

The result of the Good Governance shows that the total mean is 3.86 interpreted as Highly Evident. The result of the Risk Assessment shows that the total mean is 3.85 interpreted as Highly Evident. On the Early Warning, the total mean is 3.83 interpreted as Highly Evident. On the Knowledge Building, it shows the total mean is 3.97 interpreted as Highly Evident. On the Awareness Raising, it shows the total mean is 3.86 interpreted as Highly Evident.

DISCUSSION

On the extent is the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM)

According to UNESCO (2010), preparedness plans are dynamic ventures that need to be reviewed, modified, updated, and tested regularly. Active disaster preparedness includes developing comprehensive response plans, monitoring hazards and threats, training emergency personnel, and training members of the communities at risk “to ensure the timely appropriate and effective delivery of relief”

Table 1. Summary table extent is the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM)

Variables	Mean	Interpretation
Good Governance	3.86	Highly Evident
Risk Assessment	3.85	Highly Evident
Early Warning	3.83	Highly Evident
Knowledge Building	3.97	Highly Evident
Awareness Raising	3.86	Highly Evident
Overall Mean	3.87	Highly Evident

The tables exhibit the implementation of disaster risk reduction and management among schools in the Division of Sultan Kudarat. Interestingly, all variables were interpreted as highly evident with a computed overall mean of 3.87.

In particular, Knowledge Building got the highest mean of 3.97 which is interpreted as “Highly Evident”, followed by Good Governance and Awareness Raising got the equal computed mean of 3.86 which is interpreted as “Highly Evident”, meanwhile Early Warning got the lowest computed mean of 8.83 and Risk Assessment with a computed mean of 3.85 but it was interpreted as “Highly Evident”.

The results of the study conform with the study of Tizon (2020) that the disaster risk reduction management (DRRM) program in public schools is well implemented. Public schools are also very capable of responding to hazards in the occurrence of disasters.

In addition, there is a need to assess whether learners and educators are aware of the safety plans and are well prepared for any outbreak of disaster (Catanus, 2018). Grant (2012) stressed that disaster awareness in schools, can be incorporated in institutions through strategically posting safety rules, installing firefighting equipment, and evacuation exits, maintaining buildings, organizing seminars on disaster awareness and involving peer education, electronic and print media, action learning and using science education as a means to introduce studies of disaster risk.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The result of the study on the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management along with Good Governance, Risk Assessment, Early Warning, Knowledge Building, and Awareness Raising was found to be Highly Evident among schools in the Division Sultan Kudarat.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented:

The School DRRM coordinators may continue to implement the Disaster Risk Reduction Activities. The school may continue its best practices to strengthen the DRRM activities to avoid loss of property and lives when disaster strikes. This study be replicated in a wide scope to have a clearer picture of the implementation of DRRM activities and may add other variables which is not included in the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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